

Supplemental Data

This document contains information additional to the paper entitled “The impact of uplift on slope stability”. This document is divided into the following sections:

- Section A, photos of the final condition of the model
- Section B, Graphs of the hydraulic head at the sand – clay interface, H_s
- Section C, ratio σ_v / σ_w at the sand – clay interface
- Section D, normative slip plane found by Spencer method

These sections discuss the results of tests discussed in the corresponding paper, Test A4 to A13, B1, B2, B4 to B6.

Section A. Final condition of the tested models

The following photos show the model at the end of the test. For the tests in which slope failure developed, the photos provide a good impression of the developed failure mechanism. Most relevant details of the individual tests are given in the photos caption, more detailed information can be found in Appendix A of the corresponding paper. The images are created by stitching the photos from the left and right camera, taken at the same moment.

Figure SA.1, Test A4, $h_{clay} = 28.5$ mm, slope failure at 70 g (pre-mature failure)

Figure SA.2, Test A5, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm, slope failure at 80 g

Figure SA.3, Test A6, $h_{clay} = 29$ mm, slope failure at 99.3 g

Figure SA.4, Test A7, $h_{clay} = 58$ mm, slope failure at 100 g

Figure SA.5, Test A8, $h_{clay} = 28$ mm, no slope failure observed, geometry at 130 g

Figure SA.6, Test A9, $h_{clay} = 16$ mm, no slope failure observed, geometry at 130 g

Figure SA.7, Test A10, $h_{clay} = 28$ mm, slope failure at 91 g

Figure SA.8, Test A11, $h_{clay} = 34$ mm, slope failure at 130 g

Figure SA.9, Test A12, $h_{clay} = 65$ mm, slope failure at 120.5 g

Figure SA.10, Test A13, $h_{clay} = 16$ mm, no slope failure observed, geometry at 130 g

Figure SA.11, Test B1, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm, slope failure at 113 g

Figure SA.12, Test B2, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm, slope failure at 112 g

Figure SA.13, Test B4, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm, slope failure at 110 g

Figure SA.14, Test B5, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm, slope failure at 113 g

Figure SA.15, Test B6, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm, slope failure at 110 g

Section B, Hydraulic head, H_{sand}

The graphs below present the hydraulic head in the sand layer at the sand – clay interface. In the graphs, $H_{sand} = 0$ corresponds to the top of the sand layer. Details are presented in the corresponding paper.

Figure SB.1, Test A4, $h_{clay} = 28.5$ mm

Figure SB.2, Test A5, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Figure SB.3, Test A6, $h_{clay} = 29$ mm

Figure SB.4, Test A7, $h_{clay} = 58$ mm

Figure SB.5, Test A8, $h_{clay} = 28$ mm

Figure SB.6, Test A9, $h_{clay} = 16$ mm

Figure SB.7, Test A10, $h_{clay} = 28$ mm

Figure SB.8, Test A11, $h_{clay} = 34$ mm

Figure SB.9, Test A12, $h_{clay} = 65$ mm

Figure SB.10, Test A13, $h_{clay} = 16$ mm

Figure SB.11, Test B1, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Figure SB.12, Test B2, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Figure SB.13, Test B4, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Figure SB.14, Test B5, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Figure SB.15, Test B6, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Section C, Ratio σ_v/σ_w

The graphs below present the ratio of the total vertical total stress over the pore pressure at the clay – sand interface, $n = \sigma_v/\sigma_w$. The total vertical stress, σ_v is derived from a 1D analysis, which includes the free water on top of the cover layer. Details are given in the corresponding paper.

Figure SC.1, Test A4, $h_{clay} = 28.5$ mm

Figure SC.2, Test A5, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Figure SC.3, Test A6, $h_{clay} = 29$ mm

Figure SC.4, Test A7, $h_{clay} = 58$ mm

Figure SC.5, Test A8, $h_{clay} = 28$ mm

Figure SC.6, Test A9, $h_{clay} = 16$ mm

Figure SC.7, Test A10, $h_{clay} = 28$ mm

Figure SC.8, Test A11, $h_{clay} = 34$ mm

Figure SC.9, Test A12, $h_{clay} = 65$ mm

Figure SC.10, Test A13, $h_{clay} = 16$ mm

Figure SC.11, Test B1, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Figure SC.12, Test B2, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Figure SC.13, Test B4, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Figure SC.14, Test B5, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Figure SC.15, Test B6, $h_{clay} = 32$ mm

Section D, Calculated failure planes

The graphs below present the normative slip planes for the individual tests. The normative slip planes are found by using the Spencer method as implemented in the software package D-Stability 2025.01. More details are given in the corresponding paper. For each test, the calculations started with a wide search area, the grey surface in the graphs below, after which the search area was narrowed to find the minimum safety factor, SF. Only the final result is presented below.

Figure SD.1a, Test A5 peak strength approach, SF = 1.07

Figure SD.1b, Test A5 large strain approach, SF = 0.99

Figure SD.2a, Test A6 peak strength approach, SF = 1.08

Figure SD.2b, Test A6 large strain approach, SF = 0.95

Figure SD.3a, Test A7 peak strength approach, SF = 1.04

Figure SD.3b, Test A7 large strain approach, SF = 0.97

Figure SD.4a, Test A8 peak strength approach, SF = 1.18

Figure SD.4b, Test 8 large strain approach, SF = 1.01

Figure SD.5a, Test A9 peak strength approach, SF = 1.22

Figure SD.5b, Test A9 large strain approach, SF = 1.13

Figure SD.6a, Test A10 peak strength approach, SF = 0.99

Figure SD.6b, Test 10 large strain approach, SF = 0.96

Figure SD.7a, Test A11 peak strength approach, SF = 1.01

Figure SD.7b, Test A11 large strain approach, SF = 0.96

Figure SD.8a, Test A12 peak strength approach, SF = 1.06

Figure SD.8b, Test A12 large strain approach, SF = 0.80

Figure SD.9a, Test A13 peak strength approach, SF = 1.18

Figure SD.9b, Test A13 large strain approach, SF = 1.07

Figure SD.10a, Test B1 peak strength approach, SF = 1.02

Figure SD.2b, Test B1 large strain approach, SF = 0.95

Figure SD.11a, Test B2 peak strength approach, SF = 1.00

Figure SD.10b, Test B2 large strain approach, SF = 0.92

Figure SD.12a, Test B4 peak strength approach, SF = 1.01

Figure SD.11b, Test B4 large strain approach, SF = 0.94

Figure SD.13a, Test B5 peak strength approach, SF = 1.01

Figure SD.12b, Test B5 large strain approach, SF = 0.89

Figure SD.14a, Test B6 peak strength approach, SF = 1.05

Figure SD.13b, Test B6 large strain approach, SF = 0.88